

Study of the Complex Compounds of Some Transition Metals with Isonicotinic Acid Hydrazide

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The complex compounds of isonicotinic acid hydrazide, (L) (abbreviated 'INAH') with Ni(II), Cu(II), Fe(II), Co(II) and Pd(II) of the molecular formulae, $M_2SO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$, (where M=Ni, Cu, Fe and Co) and $M'Cl_2$, (M'=Pd) have been prepared and characterised. The structures of the complexes have been established on the basis of their elemental analysis, ir, uv and magnetic studies. The Ni(II), Cu(II), Fe(II) and Co(II)-complexes were found to be octahedral and paramagnetic, while Pd(II)-complex was concluded to be square planar and diamagnetic.

THE ligand isonicotinic acid hydrazide (INAH), which is an important antitubercular drug and has potential sites for the metal ions, has been used in the complex formation, with a view that the complexes isolated, may be of the biological importance. Certain other hydrazides of varying coordination sites for the metal ions, have been studied by the earlier workers. The present paper reports five complex compounds of INAH with nickel(II), copper (II), iron (II), cobalt(II) and palladium(II).

Materials and Ligands :

$NiSO_4 \cdot 6H_2O$, $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$, $FeSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ and $CoSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ all of E. M. analytical reagent grade and $PdCl_2$ (A.M.) grade were employed.

0.002(M) ethanolic solution of INAH was used.

Complexes :

Ni(II), Cu(II), Fe(II) and Co(II) complexes :

0.001(M) aqueous ethanolic solution of each of Ni(II), Cu(II), Fe(II) and Co(II) was treated with

0.002(M) ethanolic solution of the ligand, i.e., in 1 : 2 molar ratio and then heated on the water-bath for 1-1½ hours. The microcrystalline complexes, with characteristic colours were formed. The complexes were filtered, washed 3-4 times with alcohol and then dried over fused $CaCl_2$ in a dessicator.

Pd(II)-complex :

0.001(M) Pd(II)-solution in ethanol was treated with 0.002 (M) ethanolic solution of the ligand. The complex was isolated by treating the contents over water bath for an hour. The complex was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried over fused $CaCl_2$ as usual.

Results and Discussion

The pH values, at which the complexes were formed, colours of the complexes, results on the elemental analyses and magnetic moment values have been placed in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Complexes	pH of formation	Colours	% M found (calcd.)	% C found (calcd.)	% H found (calcd.)	% N found (calcd.)	μ_{eff} , BM (25°C)
$Ni(INAH)_2SO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$	3.5	Blue yellow	12.62 (12.63)	30.95 (30.98)	3.83 (3.87)	18.02 (18.07)	3.09
$Cu(INAH)_2SO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$	4.0	Greenish blue	13.30 (13.31)	30.60 (30.67)	3.70 (3.83)	17.82 (17.88)	2.51
$Fe(INAH)_2SO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$	4.0	Yellowish brown	12.00 (12.09)	31.10 (31.17)	3.85 (3.89)	18.06 (18.18)	5.82
$Co(INAH)_2SO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$	3.5	Pink	12.65 (12.67)	30.90 (30.97)	3.81 (3.87)	18.00 (18.06)	4.78
$Pd(INAH)_2Cl_2$	3.0	Yellow	23.56 (23.57)	31.85 (31.90)	3.06 (3.10)	18.40 (18.60)	0.00

These complexes were soluble in water, methanol and carbon tetrachloride. The complexes were found quite stable upto 130°-40°.

Magnetic moment :

Magnetic moment, μ_{eff} , for Ni(II)-complex was found to be 3.09 BM, which suggested it to be paramagnetic with octahedral structure μ_{eff} for Cu(II)-complex was determined to be 2.51 BM, which was pretty large from paramagnetism contribution due to one unpaired electron spin, although a bit less than 2.82 BM, a value corresponding of two unpaired electrons spin equivalent. The discrepancy may be explained because of a bit shift of octahedral symmetry towards the distorted octahedral one $\mu_{eff}=5.82$ BM, in case of Fe(II)-complex suggested it to be paramagnetic and octahedral¹. In case of Co(II)-complex, $\mu_{eff}=2.78$ BM, might be attributed due to high symmetry component² in octahedral geometry and also free from partial covalent character. $\mu_{eff}=0$ in case of Pd(II)-complex, showed it to be diamagnetic having square planar geometry, involving dsp² hybridisation.

U. V.-vis spectra :

U. V. -vis spectra of the complexes were studied in methanol and data were placed in Table 2.

of the band suggested the octahedral geometry of the Ni(II)-complex.

Broad band at 13422 cm⁻¹ might be regarded due to 2 E_g→2T_{2g} transition. It was found asymmetric on account of splitting by a low symmetry ligand field component. Absence of a band around 18181 cm⁻¹ discarded the possibility of square planar geometry. However, a band at 15151 cm⁻¹ suggested the distortion of octahedral geometry of the complex. The band at 23256 cm⁻¹ has been attributed due to charge transfer. All these band positions suggested the distorted octahedral geometry for Cu(II) complex.

The spectra of Fe(II)-complex showed the charge transfer band at 19387 cm⁻¹. The band at 25125 cm⁻¹ was probably due to 1A_{1g}→1T_{1g} transition, which also might be regarded a charge transfer band. A broad band at 12193 cm⁻¹ due to 5 T_{2g}→5 E_g transition suggested the octahedral geometry of Fe(II)-complex. In this case, Dq value and second and first frequencies ratio were found to be 121 cm⁻¹ and 1.51 respectively.

A very weak band of low intensity at 10746 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of Co(II)-complex has been assigned to

TABLE 2

Complexes	λ max, nm	Frequency (V) cm ⁻¹	Transitions	Dq, cm ⁻¹ B cm ⁻¹	$\frac{\nu_2}{\nu_1}$	β
Ni(INAH) ₂ SO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	402	24875 (V ₂)	3A _{2g} →3T _{1g} (P)	109	956	1.84
	520	15300 (V ₂)	3A _{2g} →3T _{1g} (F)			
	920	10967 (v ₁)	3A _{2g} →3T _{2g} (F)			
Cu(INAH) ₂ SO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	430	23256 (v ₄)	C → T	116	...	1.16
	660	15151 (v ₈)	2B ₁ →2E _g			
	745	13422 (v ₂)	2E _g →2T _{2g}			
	862	11600 (v ₁)	2B ₁ 2A _{1g}			
Fe(INAH) ₂ SO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	398	25125 (v ₂)	1A _{1g} →1T _{1g}	121	...	1.51
	515	19387 (V ₂)	C → T			
	820	12193 (v ₁)	5T _{2g} →5E _g			
Co(INAH) ₂ SO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	460	21738 (v ₂)	4T _{1g} (F)→4T _{1g} (P)	107	975	1.85
	502	19920 (v ₂)	4T _{1g} (F)→4A _{2g} (F)			
	930	10746 (v ₁)	4T _{1g} (F)→4T _{2g} (F)			
Pd(INAH) ₂ Cl ₂	280	35714 (v ₂)	C→T	243	1.29	
	320	31238 (v ₂)	1A _{1g} →1E _g			
	420	24389 (v ₁)	1A _{1g} →1B _{1g}			

The bands at 24875, 15300 and 10967 cm⁻¹ have been assigned to 3 A_{2g}→3T_{1g} (P), 3A_{2g}→3T_{1g}(F) and 3 A_{2g} → 3T_{2g} (F) respectively. Transition at 10967 cm⁻¹ might be attributed to spin allowed transition, while that at 19230 cm⁻¹ has been explained to be spin forbidden transition. Dq was found to be 109 cm⁻¹ on the basis of first frequency and ratio of v₂ and v₁ was 1.84. The spin allowed transition might be regarded due to transition arising in the complex when passing from O_h to D_{4h} symmetry. The positions

4 T_{1g} (F)→4 T_{2g} (F) transition, which explained the pink colour of the complex also. The bands at 21738 and 19920 cm⁻¹ were assigned due to 4T_{1g} (F)→4 A_{2g}(F) and 4T_{1g} (F) →4T_{1g} (P) transitions, respectively. The possibility of effect of low symmetry ligand field component on a single term might not be made a base to explain them. The first frequency showed Dq to be 107cm⁻¹ and v₂ and v₁ ratio was found to be 1.85. The positions of the bands suggested confidently the octahedral geometry of Co(II)-complex.

A band at 24389 cm^{-1} in the u.v. spectra of Pd(II)-complex has been assigned to $1A_{1g} \rightarrow 1B_{1g}$ ($a_{1g}^2 \rightarrow a_{1g}^1$, b_g^1) transition. It suggested the square planar geometry of Pd(II)-complex. The band at 31238 cm^{-1} which was shoulder on the charge transfer band at 35714 cm^{-1} was a ligand field origin probably due to $1A_{1g} \rightarrow 1E_g$ transition.

I. R. spectra :

The I. R. spectra of the ligand and complexes were studied in KBr phase between $4000\text{--}200\text{ cm}^{-1}$, and the results are placed in Table 3.

Moreover, M-O band could be formed only when oxygen atom of C=O group⁵ donated a lone pair of electrons to the metal ions or by the replacement of hydrogen atom of OH group of the enolic form⁶ (amidol system) of the ligand.

TABLE 3

INAH, cm^{-1}	Ni(II), cm^{-1}	Cu(II), cm^{-1}	Fe(II), cm^{-1}	Co(II), cm^{-1}	Pd(II), cm^{-1}	Assignments
—	3580 bs	3550 s	3530 s	3560 s		OH str. of H_2O
3430 vs	3370 s	3380 vs	3385 s	3375 s	3370 s	$\nu(\text{NH}_2)$
3310 s	3150 s	3155 ms	3145 ms	3160 ms	3150 ms	ν sym (NH)
3210 s	3060 ms	3080 vs	3075 ms	3055 ms	3065 ms	ν a sym (NH_2)
1715 s	1675 s	1670 s	1680 s	1665 ms	1675 s	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$
1640 s	1620 w	1630 w	1630 w	1635 w	1625 w	NH_2 deform or bend + OCN
1605 s	1590 s	1560 s	1565 s	1580 s	1595 s	Heterocyclic ring + ring asym (C=N)
1490 ms	1500 w	1495 w	1505 ms	1510 ms	1500 ms	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$
1250 ms	1390 ms	1390 ms	1380 ms	1395 ms	1385 ms	(NH) ν sym (C=N)
	1200 w	1195 ms	1205 ws	1210 ms	1205 w	(NH)
	1130 vs	1130 vs	1125 vs	1135 vs		SO_4^{2-}
	1105 s	1100 s	1110 s	1105 s	1110 s	(C-O)
995 w	995 w	990 w	985 w	990 w	995 w	N-N made
950 w	950 w	945 w	945 w	950 w		C-H out of plane deform or SO_4^{2-}
890 s	890 ms	890 ms	885 ms	890 ms	885 ms	ring with 2 H adjacent + NH out of plane bend.
	785 s	790 s	780 ms	785 s		coordinated H_2O
745 s	745 s	745 s	740 s	750 s	745 s	Mono substituted ring
685 ms	685 ms	685 ms	680 ms	685 ms	680 ms	(C=O) out of plane
	630 s	640 ms	635 ms	635 ms		Coordinated H_2O
580 w	575 w	570 w	565 w	565 w	570 w	NH_2 rocking.
	530 bw	520 w	530 ms	540 ms	510 ms	(M-O)
	520 w	510 bs	500 w	505 w	508 ms	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$
	500 ms	490 s				$\nu(\text{M}-\text{O}) + \nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$
460 w	465 w	470 w	465 w	470 w	465 w	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ in plane.

The band at 3430 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{NH}_2)$, in the spectrum of the ligands³ was found to decrease at $3370, 3380, 3385, 3375$ and 3370 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the Ni(II), Cu(II), Fe(II), Co(II) and Pd(II) complexes respectively, showing that the coordination has taken place through nitrogen atom of NH_2 group of the hydrazine residue.

The bands at $3580, 3550, 3530$ and 3560 cm^{-1} in the Ni(II), Cu(II), Fe(II) and Co(II)-complexes have been assigned to OH stretching frequencies of the coordinated water molecules.

Further, the appearance of the bands of medium intensities around $630\text{--}640\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the sharp bands around $780\text{--}790\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of Ni(II), Cu(II), Fe(II) and Co(II)-complexes suggested that two water molecules⁴ were coordinated to the respective metal ions.

At a glance, the latter probability appeared more evident due to the steric hindrance of the aromatic heterocyclic ring, linked with the carbonyl carbon atom, adjacent to which was NH group of the hydrazine residue. Due to that, H atom of NH group would contribute more to greater electronegative oxygen atom of C=O group, rather than to immino nitrogen atom.

Which one of the forms III and IV (both having requisite sites) responsible for the complex formation

might be concluded on the basis of presence of $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$ which was observed at 1490 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the ligand shifted to $1500, 1495, 1505, 1510$ and 1500 cm^{-1} in the Ni(II), Cu(II), Fe(II), Co(II) and Pd(II)-complexes respectively. Thus form III seemed more prominent for the coordination than the form IV, which might be prominent at high pH values, where replacement of H atom or deprotonation appeared easier.

$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ frequency which was observed in 1715 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the ligand, shifted downwards¹ at $1675, 1670, 1680, 1665$ and 1675 cm^{-1} in the Ni(II), Cu(II), Fe(II), Co(II) and Pd(II)-complexes respectively. This suggested that the coordination had taken place through oxygen atom of C=O group. After coordination intensities remained unchanged. Due to the coordination, a loss of lone pair of electrons of oxygen atom was further compensated by the electrons of C=O bond, which resulted into a decrease of double bond character of C=O group and consequently increase of C-N double bond character^{1,7}.

The band at 1250 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the ligand splitted into two components, i.e., in the ranges, $(1195-1210)$ and $(1380-1395)\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the complexes. The latter components might be due to $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{C}=\text{N})$, developed in the spectra of the complex due to increase of (C-N) double bond character. Sharp bands between $(1605-1560)\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the ligand and the complexes were assigned to the aromatic ring including (C=N) asymmetric frequency of the ring. The bands around $(1110-1100)\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the complexes, which were assigned to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ frequencies⁸, appeared after coordination of carbonyl oxygen atom to metal ions and decrease of double bond character of C=O. The appearance of $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ frequencies in the complexes, might not be explained in terms of the replacement of H atom of the enolic ligand, because the complexes have been formed at low pH values where deprotonation appeared difficult⁸.

Further the very sharp bands around $(1135-1125)\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the complexes [except Pd(II)], have been assigned to the ionic nature of sulphate group^{8,9} with T_d -symmetry in the complexes.

The sharp band at 640 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the ligand was assigned due to NH_2 deformation, associated with OCN band shifted downwards around $(1635-1620)\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes and diminished the frequencies. The bands around $(995-985)$, $(950-945)$ and $(890-885)\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the ligand and complexes have been assigned to

N-N mode of vibration¹, C-H out of plane deformation and heterocyclic ring having two adjacent hydrogen atoms⁹, probably coupled with the band due to NH out of plane deformation respectively.

The ir spectra of Ni(II)-complex showed broad diffused nature of bands in the region $3600-3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ probably due to overlap of NH, NH_2 and OH mode of coordinated water molecules⁸.

The low frequency bands at $530, 520, 530, 540$ and 510 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the complexes only, were assigned to $\nu(\text{Ni}-\text{O}), \nu(\text{Cu}-\text{O}), \nu(\text{Fe}-\text{O}), \nu(\text{Co}-\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{Pd}-\text{O})$ respectively^{8,4}. Sahni and others¹ observed $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ at still lower frequencies in the complexes of pentadentate ligand having identical system and trivalent metals.

The bands at $520, 510, 500, 505$ and 508 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the complexes have been assigned to $\nu(\text{Ni}-\text{N}), \nu(\text{Cu}-\text{N}), \nu(\text{Fe}-\text{N}), \nu(\text{Co}-\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{Pd}-\text{N})$ respectively^{1,4}. The spectrum of Pd(II)-complex did not show the bands for the coordinated water molecules.

On the basis of the above evidences, it has been concluded that the ligand is neutral and bidentate in nature and the tentative structures of the electrolytic cationic complexes can be represented as follows :-

(VIII)

Where, M = Ni, Cu, Fe and Co.

(IX)

Where, $\text{M}^1 = \text{Pd}$.

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